

Traffic Behavior on São Paulo's Streets: A Post-Pandemic Study

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Abstract: This study examines São Paulo's post-COVID-19 traffic conditions after adopting a new data collection system in partnership with Waze. São Paulo, with over 6 million cars, 12 million people, and 20,000 km of roads, analyzed data from May 2020 to September 2023. Traffic patterns varied significantly on different weekdays. Mondays had lower volume (6.7 million vehicles) and congestion (76 km), while Tuesdays and Wednesdays had intermediate levels (6.6 million vehicles and 100 km, respectively). Thursdays and Fridays showed higher volume (6.7 million vehicles) and increased congestion (110 km). The study demonstrated a strong relationship between volume and traffic slowdown, reflecting economic recovery.

Keywords: Traffic Analysis; Traffic Patterns; Traffic Behavior; Traffic Congestion; Covid-19

1. Contextualization

The intense circulation of vehicles is a reality in the largest urban agglomerations, constituting a problem not only for drivers, but also for traffic managers, generating slowdowns on roads and long travel times, greatly impacting mobility in the urban environment [1]. Urban mobility is configured as a human need in its search for work, food, fun and knowledge.

The first case of Covid in humans was confirmed in November 2019 and the first case in Brazil was confirmed in February 2020. The Brazilian Governor decree a quarantine period in March 2020 [2]. This situation has imposed a radical change in the logic of urban travel, drastically affecting all forms of transport, including private transportation by car.

Gradually, the flows were being reinstated as social distancing measures were relaxed, and as the pandemic was nearing its end, a complete return of economic activities took place, consequently resulting in the resumption of urban flows, both for public transportation passengers and private cars on city roads. In this manner, the return of cars occurred, leading to congestion and traffic slowdown in urban roads.

This paper analyzes the average daily data on the number of cars and slowdowns on the streets of São Paulo from May 2020, when a new car and road monitoring system was implemented in partnership with the Waze application [3], until September 2023, to verify traffic behavior during the post-pandemic period. The comparison with previous data is greatly affected due to the divergences in the measurement methods used until 2019 and from 2020 onwards.

2. Place and method of study

This study was carried out in the city of São Paulo (Figure 1), the capital of the State of São Paulo in Brazil, which has a population of over 12 million inhabitants, making it the fifth most populous city in the world, 6.2 million cars, more than 20 thousand km of urban roads. The Metropolitan Region of São Paulo (MRSP) has more 38 cities, collectively hosting over 22 million inhabitants and nearly 9.9 million automobiles, many of which utilize the urban roadways of the capital for their daily commutes [4, 5, 6].

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Figure 1. Location of the City of São Paulo (dark gray) in the MRSP (light gray) and in Brazil. Adapted from [7]

3. Results and discussions

Using the daily data on car volume and slowdowns, it was possible to verify the behavior for each of the workdays. For volume traffic (Figure 2(a)) the data focuses on the range between 6 and 7 million cars, staying above this threshold only in the 4th quarter of 2022 and 1st quarter of 2023. For slowdown (Figure 2(b)) the data fluctuate in the range of 50 to 150 km until the 3rd quarter of 2022, when they rise to the range of 100 to 200 km. The outliers represent holidays and the eve of holidays or atypical days due to flood, strikes or other specific reasons, or the recovery of the economy, for the data of the 2nd quarter of 2020.

Figure 2. Daily plot, with quarterly breakdown, of data from May 2020 to September 2023 of: (a) average traffic volume on each day of the week; (b) average slowdown on each day of the week. The red vertical lines represent the semi-annual (full) and quarterly (dashed) division.

Analyzing Figure 2(a), it is possible to see that, in the lanes above 6 million vehicles, traffic on Mondays occupies the lower part and on Thursdays and Fridays the upper part. Analyzing Figure 2(b) it is possible to see that Mondays have the least slowdowns and Thursdays and Fridays have the greatest slowdowns. This analysis already shows that traffic segmentation is taking place, with fewer vehicles on the roads at the beginning of the week and more vehicles at the end of the week.

Figure 3(a) shows the relationship of traffic volume to daily slowdowns and trend lines for each day. The trends are parallel, the exception being Thursday, which shows subtle downward trend. Figure 3(b), as well as Table 1, shows the relationship between the overall average volume of vehicles and slowdowns for each of the days of the week. It is possible to verify the formation of 3 blocks: block 1 on Mondays (6.39 million vehicles and 76.23 km); block 2 on Tuesdays and Wednesdays (average of 6.60 million vehicles and

100.14 km); and Block 3 on Thursdays and Fridays (average of 6.70 million vehicles and 110.32 km). On average, from block 1 to block 2 and block 3, 200,000 and 300,000 cars are inserted, respectively, while from block 2 to block 3, an average of 100,000 cars are inserted on the city's roads. The slowdown increases on average, from block 1 to block 2 and block 3, respectively around 24 km and 34 km, and from block 2 to block 3 by an average of 10 km.

Figure 3. Plotting the ratio of daily traffic volume to daily slowdowns for: (a) each of the days of the week; (b) overall average for each day of the week.

Table 1. Overall daily average of the ratio of volume of vehicles to slowdowns on the streets.

	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri
Traffic volume (millions)	6.388	6.597	6.608	6.696	6.695
Slowdown (km)	76.23	99.66	100.62	110.32	109.83

Table 2 shows the variation in the growth of the volume of cars and slowdowns on the roads based on the values obtained for Mondays and for the averages of the blocks formed by Tuesdays and Wednesdays and Thursdays and Fridays. The average volume growth is relatively low (3.4% and 4.8%) but generates a high growth in the average slowdown (31.4% and 44.4%).

Table 2. Average volume and slowdown for Tuesdays-Wednesdays (block 2) and Thursday-Fridays (block 2) and the variation based on the values of Mondays (block 1).

	Value Mon (block 1)	Average Tue-Wed (block 2)	Variation block 1 to block 2	Average Thu-Fri (block 3)	Variation block 1 to block 3
Traffic (millions)	6.388	6.603	3.36%	6.696	4.81%
Slowdown (km)	76.23	100.14	31.37%	110.08	44.40%

Analyzing the monthly variation in daily volumes (Figure 4(a)) and the monthly variation in daily traffic slowdown (Figure 4(b)), we observe that the annual average of monthly volume increased moderately by 3.1% in 2021, 4.3% in 2022, and 3.6% by September 2023, based on 2020 data. On the other hand, the annual average of monthly traffic slowdown significantly increased, with a growth of 16.8% in 2021, 27.8% in 2022, and 17.5% by September 2023, also based on 2020 data. This aligns with the fact that, until reaching a congestion situation, even a small addition of vehicles substantially increases traffic congestion on the roads [1]. This indicates that, as of September 2023, the flow of cars on the roads is steadily increasing year after year, leading to a potential exacerbation of urban road conditions in the city.

Figure 4. Comparison between the average monthly change in working days of the average number of vehicles and the average slowdown with the total number of vehicles and the total monthly slowdown.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of traffic and slowdown data on the streets of São Paulo from May 2020 to September 2023 reveals a complex and dynamic landscape of urban mobility in Brazil's largest metropolis. The COVID-19 pandemic triggered significant changes in urban mobility patterns, resulting in a temporary interruption of congestion, followed by a gradual return to normalcy as social distancing measures were eased. However, the resurgence of traffic, particularly on Thursdays and Fridays, led to significant increases in traffic congestion, clearly demonstrating the relationship between the volume of vehicles and congestion on urban roads.

The data also indicates that, as the years progressed, both the average volume of vehicles and the average congestion levels increased. This suggests that the issue of urban mobility in the city of São Paulo is worsening. This trend reflects the growing pressure on transportation infrastructure, highlighting the need for more effective traffic management strategies and investments in infrastructure to address the challenges of urban mobility in densely populated urban areas. Furthermore, the analysis underscores the importance of understanding traffic patterns and their variations over time to enhance the quality of life and transportation efficiency in cities.

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